

STUDIES IN ORGANO-ARSENIC COMPOUNDS. PART VIII. SYNTHESIS OF ARSINDOLE DERIVATIVES FROM PHENYLACETYLENE

BY HIRENDRA NATH DAS-GUPTA.

The adducts of the primary arylarsenious halides have been prepared. In the formation of the adducts arsenic attaches itself to the α -carbon atom of the unsaturated grouping with simultaneous ring-closure.

Fischer and Klemperer (*Der Therapie der Gegenwart*, 1-3, Jan. 1913) studied the action of arsenic trichloride on aliphatic unsaturated compounds. Fischer (*Annalen*, 1914, 403, 106) investigated its action on behenic acid, but the structure of the chloroarsenobehenic acid was not actually determined, though there was hardly any doubt about the addition at the triple bond. Mannich (*Arch. Pharm.*, 1935, 273, 275) reacted it with 1-phenyl-1 : 3-diethylaminopropine ($\text{PhC}\equiv\text{C}\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{NEt}_2$) with the idea of getting an analogous compound. But the reaction failed to give a simple adduct. One of the products was found to be an arsenical ring compound analogous to indole. The formation of the latter involved an unstable addition product of the propine base with arsenic trichloride.

The work of Mochnac and Bagniuk (*Compt. rend.*, URSS., 1937, 14, 535) on the action of arsenic trichloride on behenic acid and stearolic acid on the one hand and tetrolic or ethylpropionic acid on the other, shows the influence of temperature on the nature of the resultant product.

In the present paper adducts have been formed with primary aryl arsenious halide. The addition takes place in such a way that the arsenic attaches itself to the α -carbon of the unsaturated grouping and simultaneous ring-closure occurs.

Phenylacetylene and phenyldichloroarsine reacted with evolution of hydrogen chloride at 120° . The resultant product was found to be an arsenical ring compound in which the ring formation had taken place *via* the intermediate addition compound of phenylacetylene and phenyldichloroarsine thus :

By an alternative mechanism the product (I) may be formulated as $R=Cl$ and $R'=Ph$.

But oxidation of the arsindole derivative leads to the formation of *o*-carboxydiphenylarsinic acid, the m.p. and mixed m.p. of the oxidation product being identical with that from anthranilic acid and phenylarsenious oxide (Sakellarios, *Ber.*, 1926, 59, 2552). This proves the validity of formula (I) and also that the arsenic is in cyclic combination.

It was observed that the temperature influenced the nature of the product to a considerable extent; at an elevated temperature the resultant mass comprised of a mixture of solids and liquids of indefinite composition.

1-Phenyl-3-chloroarsindole is a yellow liquid with a greenish tinge, possessing a less offensive odour than 1-chloroarsindole. It gives a yellow crystalline picrate, mercuric chloride addition product and arsonium salts.

EXPERIMENTAL.

1-Phenyl-3-chloroarsindole (I, $R=Ph$, $R'=Cl$)—A mixture of phenylacetylene (10 g.) and phenylarsenious chloride (28 g.) was heated under reflux for 7 hours at $140-50^\circ$. The mass gradually darkened with a rise in temperature and at $120-22^\circ$ there was much evolution of hydrogen chloride. The resultant dark brown viscous mass was treated with absolute alcohol with vigorous stirring, when a yellow crystalline arsenic-free solid, undergoing decomposition on exposure to air, was obtained. The filtrate was heated under reduced pressure till all the alcohol was removed and the resulting brown oil was fractionated and portions boiling (i) at $130-55^\circ/12$ mm. and (ii) at $165-75^\circ/12$ mm. were collected. The second fraction, turbid in appearance, was treated with ether, filtered from insoluble matter and the filtrate redistilled at $168-75^\circ/10$ mm., when a yellow oil was obtained. [Found: C, 58.1; H, 3.4; Cl, 12.5; As, 25.8; M.W. (cryoscopic in benzene), 285.9. $C_{14}H_{10}ClAs$ requires C, 58.2; H, 3.4; Cl, 12.3; As, 25.9 per cent. M.W., 288.5] The picrate was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. $115-16^\circ$

1-Phenyl-3-chloroarsindole mercurichloride.—Molecular proportions of (I) and mercuric chloride were taken in alcohol and heated till the mixture went completely into solution and then allowed to cool. The mercuric chloride adduct separated out in flakes and was recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. $232-33^\circ$. (Found: Hg, 35.6. $C_{14}H_{10}Cl_3AsHg$ requires Hg, 35.7 per cent).

Methiodide of (I) was prepared by heating 1-phenyl-3-chloroarsindole with excess of methyl iodide in a sealed tube at 110° for 14 hours. Excess of methyl iodide was removed in *vacuo* and the resulting brown pasty mass was extracted several times with petroleum ether which on evaporation gave needle-shaped crystals. These were recrystallised from minimum quantity of alcohol, m.p. 152-53°. (Found: As, 17.9. $C_{15}H_{13}ClIAs$ requires As, 17.6 per cent).

Ethiodide derivative was prepared in a similar way with ethyl iodide, m.p. 161° after crystallisation from alcohol in needles. (Found: As, 16.5. $C_{16}H_{15}ClIAs$ requires As, 16.8 per cent).

Oxidation of 1-phenyl-3-chloroarsindole: Formation of o-Carboxydi-phenylarsinic Acid.—1-Phenyl-3-chloroarsindole was treated with excess of perhydrol (30 vols.) when a vigorous reaction ensued. After the vigour of the reaction had subsided the whole was evaporated to dryness on a steam-bath. This was repeated several times with fresh additions of perhydrol and the solid obtained was crystallised from water, m.p. and mixed m.p. with Sakellario's compound, 166°. (Found: As, 24.1. Calc. for $C_{13}H_{11}O_4As$: As, 24.5 per cent).

APPLIED CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE,
CALCUTTA.

Received August 22, 1938.